

3D printed diplexer metalized with electroless plating technology

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Abstract — In this paper, a novel three-port diplexer based on 3D printed resonant cavities operating at X band is presented. It has one input port and two output ports with a center frequency of about 10 GHz. The design and simulation of the diplexer was carried out using the HFSS software. For device fabrication, 3D printing is used to provide a lightweight structure with low cost, prototyped in a short time. Electroless plating technology is used for device metallization. A good agreement between simulations and measurements is obtained.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diplexers are key components in various communication systems, including radio transmission, cellular radio, satellite communication systems, and broadband wireless communications. Diplexers are passive devices, used to implement frequency domain multiplexing and allow various frequencies to share common channel or antenna. Diplexers are often used as front-end equipment in communication systems, typically connected between antenna and transceiver equipment. Many technologies are used to design diplexers, e.g. SIW in [1]. They allow a transmitter and receiver operating at different frequencies to share a common antenna with a minimum interaction between the transmitted and received signals.

In this paper, we present a novel all resonator diplexer based on rectangular waveguide technology that operates at a frequency of approximately 10 GHz.

With its low losses and high-quality factor, Rectangular waveguides have always been the most efficient structures. Since they are made of bulk metal, these components are expensive with high weight, which represents the main disadvantage. With the increasing development of new communication systems, the industry needs lightweight components with fast manufacturing and low cost. 3D printing is a good option to reduce weight using dielectric resins. To metalize the structure with a thick layer of metal, copper in this

design, electroless plating technology is used. Other devices are fabricated using these methods [2,3,4] in this paper an X-band diplexer is shown for the first time.

II. DESIGN & SIMULATION

A. Rectangular waveguide Diplexer Design

The diplexer design is divided into three sections to reduce design complexity, sections of two resonators are simulated as a first design step. The quality factor is measured using an external port and a coupled resonator. Every section was designed individually using Ansoft HFSS and optimized to get the best simulation results. Finally, all sections are assembled and optimized to produce the diplexer design.

Fig 1:3D view of the proposed diplexer

The X band diplexer is designed using 6 waveguide cavity resonators. Fig.1 shows a 3D view of the diplexer with port dimensions. The resonators are coupled together with inductive irises. The diplexer has a pass-band center frequency of 9.75 GHz for channel 1 and 10.45 GHz for channel 2. The mathematical modelling and methodology are developed to design this project using Ansoft HFSS. Simultaneously, the whole design was divided into sections to simplify complexity.

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Each pair of coupled resonators was simulated separately to find the coupling iris corresponding to the required coupling coefficient. Finally, each section assembled together to form a complete design. The corresponding simulation results are carefully performed and optimized to get the desired output for each coupled resonator section. The physical dimensions of $a=22.86$ mm, $b=10.16$ mm was used, which are the standard dimensions for rectangular waveguide operating at X-band, thus this diplexer is based on the WR-90 waveguide structure to take into account the RF measurement setup. The weak coupling was set $t=3$ mm throughout the design. Fig. 1 shows a 3D view of the proposed diplexer with the input port, Port 1 and two output ports, 2 and 3, respectively as well as all cavities and inductive irises. The coupling values between the cavities and the external quality factor are shown in Table 1.

B. Simulation

Simulation results of the designed all resonator diplexer are obtained using the high frequency FEM simulation software (Ansoft HFSS), after designing the diplexer, $10\mu\text{m}$ of the structure surface is removed and replaced by copper metal, the dielectric chosen is perfect vacuum, since the structure is covered with metal, the dielectric structural material does not have any effect on the simulations.

Table 1: coupling matrix and external Q-factor of the proposed diplexer

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	0	0.0853	0	0	0	0
2	0.0853	0	0.0415	0	0.0415	0
3	0	0.0415	-0.0577	0.0373	0	0
4	0	0	0.0373	-0.0643	0	0
5	0	0.0415	0	0	0.0577	0.0373
6	0	0	0	0	0.0373	0.0643
	Port1	Port2	Port3			
Qext	11.7834	22.8	22.8			

Fig 2: Comparison between measurement and simulation results

Fig. 2 shows the optimized S-parameters simulation results. The insertion loss of the first band [9.5-10] GHz is negligible

and the return loss less than 10dB, with a center frequency of 9.75GHz. For the second band [10.15-10.65] GHz, the insertion loss is negligible and the return loss about 10dB, with a center frequency of 10.45GHz. The bandwidth of the two X-band diplexer bands is about 500MHz.

III. FABRICATION

The waveguide Diplexer was fabricated using a commercial 3D printer (Form 2, Form labs, Inc.). In this study, the diplexer is fabricated in two parts, built separately. The first part contains all resonators and the second part is just a cover. The 3D printed diplexer structure has a whole size of $134.9 \times 67 \times 42.16$ mm³ and very light-weight compared with a conventionally fabricated all-metallic rectangular waveguide device.

In order to metallize the surface of the printed structure, an electroless plating method, based on a commercialized copper plating process, is employed in this study. After metallizing the two parts of the diplexer, the two pieces are assembled with screws and nuts.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Measurement and simulation results in Fig. 2 show a good agreement, and demonstrate that RF frequencies can share a common channel, where frequency domain multiplexing can be implemented using the fabricated diplexer. However, the diplexer has a central frequency shift from 9.7 GHz to 9.6 GHz, for the first band, and from 10.45GHz to 10.3 GHz for the second band. After the metallization of the diplexer structure, a slight non-uniformity of the metal surface is obtained, after device assembly, leakage loss is observed during measurements, which caused the frequency shift and higher losses compared to the simulations.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, 3D printing and electroless plating methods are used to produce a rectangular waveguide-based diplexer. After 3D printing, a $10\mu\text{m}$ thick copper metal layer is deposited on the surface of the printed pieces. Finally, simulation results are compared with actual measurements. There is a good agreement between simulation and measurement results, which shows that 3D printing can be used to make high-performance RF circuits.

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